

Susceptibility of promising rice cultivars to whitebacked planthopper

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The whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, previously a minor rice pest, is becoming a threat at the crop's early tillering stage with the introduction of high yielding varieties and high-input technology. Thirty-nine rice cultivars (see table) were evaluated against WBPH attack in the field in 1977 kharif. The rices were transplanted in two advanced trials in the last week of June in a completely randomized block experiment with three replicates. The pest population on 15 hills/replication was recorded in the last week of August when pest incidence was at its peak. RP633-519-1-3-4-1 harbored the lowest population (6.5) and IR36 the next lowest (8.5). The maximum infestation was on Prasad (47.3). No cultivar was immune to WBPH attack. Rasi (IET1444), which was planted in an agronomic trial, suffered heavily; it had 400 to 500 insects/hill or more. ■

Whitebacked planthopper populations on promising rice cultivars. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Designation	Av population (no./hill)
<i>Medium duration</i>	
RP6-516-31-4	34.4
UPR103-44-1-1-1-1-2	32.5
Jaya	32.3
UPRI 73-23	38.8
CR75-93	29.4
CR167-10	28.3
BG90-2	26.9
IR2153-26-3-5-2	25.9
UPR84-30-1-2-1-3	25.2
UPR70x30-4-1	24.2
CR164-12	24.1
UPRI 73-18	22.7
IR2151-190-3-5	22.5
CR94-MR 1550	21.3
CR129-118	21.0
UPR243-247-1	20.6
RP632-94-1-2-1-7	16.1
BG35-2	15.9
S52134	15.6
TC-A-1-P2-5-2	15.3
BR 34-13-5	15.1
IR36	8.5
RP633-519-1-3-4-1	6.5
C.D. at 5%	11.85

Designation	(no./hill)
<i>Early duration</i>	
Prasad	47.3
UPR103D-7-1	37.7
Pusa 33	35.6
UPRI75-4	33.0
CR142-3-2	31.9
UPR221-124-1	31.6
UPR103-80-1-2-1-2	31.0
UPR83D-8-1	31.0
UPR4D-1-3-1	29.3
OR34-16	23.4
UPR190D-17-1	22.0
Pusa 2-21	22.0
UPR4D-1-1	17.7
IR2061-487-1-19	17.4
UPR82-1-7	13.2
RP1158-85-1	12.1
CD at 5%	10.99

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deepwater

Screening deepwater rice varieties in different water regimes

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Twenty-five deepwater rice varieties, along with Pankaj, were screened for elongation capacity, nodal differentiation,

and internode elongation in two sets of experiments. In the first set, 30-day-old potted seedlings were suspended in a water column 80 cm deep in cement tanks (Photo 1). In the other set the seeds were germinated in a 40-cm water column in glass jars in the laboratory (Photo 2). One set of potted plants was also grown under normal conditions.

1. Cement tank used in screening deepwater rices. CRR, Cuttack, India.